

Solvatochromism and Prototropism of 4-Hydroxybiphenyl. A Study by Electronic Spectra

M. SWAMINATHAN

Department of Chemistry, Periyar Arts College, Cuddalore-607 001

Manuscript received 4 April 1988, accepted 18 July 1988

Analysis of the absorption and fluorescence spectral shifts of 4-hydroxybiphenyl in different solvents indicate that in the ground state hydrogen acceptor interaction of the compound is more predominant whereas in the excited singlet state its hydrogen donor interaction is more effective. The excited state acidity constants, determined by different methods are reported and discussed. It is found that 4-hydroxybiphenyl is more acidic in the S_1 state than in the S_0 state.

4-Hydroxybiphenyl (BOH) is found to be a biologically and industrially important compound^{1,2}. The absorption and fluorescence spectra of the compound were reported during a study of phenol derivatives³. But its electronic spectral characteristics were not studied elaborately. In a series of papers⁴⁻⁷ we investigated the absorption and fluorescence characteristics of several hydroxy and amino compounds. The present investigation was carried out to study the effect of solvents and pH on the absorption and fluorescence spectra of 4-hydroxybiphenyl.

Experimental

4-Hydroxybiphenyl (Aldrich) was purified by recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol. The purity of BOH was checked by obtaining identical fluorescence when excited at different wavelengths. Triple-distilled water was used to prepare the aqueous solutions. Spectrograde methanol, acetonitrile and hexane (all B.D.H.) were used as such. Absorption spectra were recorded using a JASCO UNIDEC-650 spectrophotometer and fluorescence measurements were made using a JASCO FP-550 spectrofluorimeter. pH values in the range 1-13 were measured on a Systronics 330 digital pH meter. The solutions were prepared just before taking spectral measurements. The concentrations of the solutions were of the order 10^{-5} - 10^{-4} M.

Results and Discussion

Solvatochromism: The absorption maxima, $\log \epsilon$ and fluorescence maxima of BOH in different solvents and in alkaline solution are given in Table 1. The absorption and fluorescence spectra are shown in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. When compared to hexane, the absorption maxima in other solvents are red-shifted. In alkaline solution (pH \approx 14), where deprotonation occurs, the absorption maxima is further red-shifted. But in water

and methanol a blue-shift relative to the maxima in acetonitrile is observed. The blue-shift is maximum in water. On the other hand, there is a regular red-shift of fluorescence with the increase in polarity and hydrogen bonding capacity of solvents. Deprotonation in alkaline solution also gives a red-shift.

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION MAXIMA ($\bar{\nu}_{abs}$), $\log \epsilon$ AND FLUORESCENCE MAXIMA ($\bar{\nu}_{flu}$) AT 298 K IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvent	$\bar{\nu}_{abs}$ cm ⁻¹	$\log \epsilon$	$\bar{\nu}_{flu}$ cm ⁻¹
Hexane	39 216		30 120
Acetonitrile	38 424	4.33	29 850
Methanol	38 499	4.28	29 674
Water	38 685	4.27	29 326
Alkaline solution (pH \approx 14)	34 813	4.31	24 752

Amino and hydroxy groups can act as a bifunctional system since they contain both lone-pair of electrons and acidic hydrogen atom. In case of a hydroxy group, it can interact with hydrogen-donating solvents through its lone-pair or with hydrogen-accepting solvents through its hydrogen atom. Thus with the increase in hydrogen bonding capacity of the solvents, a blue-shift in the former case and a red-shift in the latter should be observed. This explains the red-shift observed in hydrogen-acceptor solvent, acetonitrile. Blue-shifts in methanol and water when compared to acetonitrile indicates hydrogen donor interactions are predominant in these two solvents. Furthermore, the maximum blue-shift observed in water shows that hydrogen donating capability of water is more than that of methanol. Similar behaviour of water has been observed in the study of 9-phenanthrol⁸.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of 4-hydroxybiphenyl in different solvents at 298 K: (○) hexane, (Δ) acetonitrile, (---) water, (●) methanol and (×) alkaline solution.

Hence hydrogen acceptor interaction of the solvent is predominant in the excited singlet state. Thus a continuous red-shift is observed from hexane to water. In solvents methanol and water, the site of interaction in the excited singlet state is found to be different from the site of interaction in the ground state.

Prototropism: In water, BOH exists as neutral form, but when pH is increased above 11, deprotonation leading to the formation of an ion occurs as

The absorption and fluorescence spectra of neutral form (water solution) and anion (alkaline solution) are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 along with the spectra in other solvents. During deprotonation both absorption and fluorescence maxima are red-shifted. The excited state pK_a values (pK_a^*) at 298 K for the above equilibrium were calculated from the results of fluorimetric titration and using methods based on Förster cycle⁹. The pK_a^* values obtained are given in Table 2. The pK_a^* values obtained from both absorption and fluorescence data indicate that the

Fig. 2. Fluorescence spectra of 4-hydroxybiphenyl in different solvents at 298 K: (○) hexane, (Δ) acetonitrile, (---) water, (●) methanol and (×) alkaline solution.

In the excited singlet state the polarity of the O-H is further increased due to the increased charge transfer interaction of the lone-pair of the hydroxy group. This increased charge transfer interaction is also shown by the loss of structure in the fluorescence spectrum of BOH when compared to the fluorescence of biphenyl⁸ in a non-polar solvent. This leads to the interaction of the hydrogen atom of the hydroxy group with the solvent.

TABLE 2—GROUND AND EXCITED SINGLET STATE ACIDITY CONSTANTS OF 4-HYDROXYBIPHENYL

pK_a	$pK_a^*(\text{abs})$	$pK_a^*(\text{flu})$	$pK_a^*(\text{ave})$	$pK_a^*(\text{FT})$
10.88 ^a	2.75	0.73	1.74	9.65

^aRef. 10.

compound becomes more acidic in the excited singlet state. But there is a difference of about 2 pK_a units between the two values. This difference is due to unequal solvent relaxation and geometry change between S_0 and S_1 states of the species involved in the equilibrium. BOH undergoes a change in geometry, i.e. attains more planarity during excitation. A change in nuclear conformation has also been reported for biphenyl¹¹ and 3,5-diphenylpyrazole¹². The pK_a^* , obtained by fluorimetric titration, is near to the ground state pK_a value. This indicates that the equilibrium is not established during the life-time of the excited state, i.e. excited species loses its energy before undergoing deprotonation. Similar behaviour has been observed for many heterocyclic molecules¹².

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to the U. G. C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. J. M. GOTTESFELD, N. H. ADAMS, A. M. EL BADRY, V. MOSES and M. CALVIN, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1971, 228, 365.
2. G. WEKLER, *Text. Prax. Int*, 1973, 28, 393.
3. P. G. SENNIKOV and V. A. KUZNETSOV, *Zh. Obsch. Khim*, 1980, 50, 2761.
4. M. SWAMINATHAN and S. K. DOGRA, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1983, 61, 1064.
5. M. SWAMINATHAN and S. K. DOGRA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 105, 6223.
6. M. SWAMINATHAN and S. K. DOGRA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1984, 947.
7. A. K. MISHRA, M. SWAMINATHAN and S. K. DOGRA, *J. Photochem.*, 1985, 28, 87.
8. I. B. BERLMAN, "Handbook of Fluorescence Spectra of Aromatic Molecules", Academic, New York, 1965.
9. TH. FORSTER, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1950, 54, 42.
10. D. TADENSZ, *Rocz. Chem.*, 1970, 44, 61.
11. I. B. BERLMAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, 74, 3085.
12. M. SWAMINATHAN and S. K. DOGRA, *J. Photochem.*, 1983, 21, 245; S. G. SCHULMAN and A. C. CAPAMACCHIA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1972, 58, 91; S. G. SCHULMAN, R. T. TIDWELL, J. J. CETORELLI and J. D. WINEFORDENER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 93, 3179; M. SWAMINATHAN and S. K. DOGRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 278; M. SWAMINATHAN and S. K. DOGRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 853.